

DNA topoisomerase II α (TOP2A) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : TOP2A belongs to the family of topoisomerases, which regulates the (un)winding of the DNA due to its double helical structure. The main function of TOP2A is to relieve the topological stress during DNA transcription, assist in separation of chromatids and condensation of chromosomes. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of HJURP, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: TOP2A, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

^{*}ML dicoveries of TOP2A synergy in Meningiomas

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Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Meningioma	2
1.1.1	World Health Organization (WHO) classification	2
1.1.2	Historical perspective	3
1.1.3	Pathophysiology	3
1.2	DNA topoisomerase II α (TOP2A)	4
1.3	Insight behind the work	7
1.4	Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution	7
2	Methods	8
2.1	Static data from Patel et al. [1]	8
2.2	Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]	8
2.3	Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R	9
2.4	Regarding biological insight	10
3	Results & Discussion	10
3.1	TOP2A related synergies	10
3.1.1	FOXMI/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3]	10
3.1.2	TOP2A unknown combinations with high ranking	11
4	Conclusion	13
5	References	15

1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [4]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [5]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [6] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [7], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [8] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [9]. Finally, Cushing [10] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [13] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [11] and Pamir et al. [12]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. DNA topoisomerase II α (TOP2A)

From T4 bacteriophage-infected Escherichia coli cells, Liu et al. [14] purified a novel ATP-dependent DNA topoisomerase which makes reversible double-strand breaks in the DNA double helix. Their genetic data suggested that this activity was essential for initiating T4 DNA replication forks in vivo.

Miller et al. [15] purified to apparent homogeneity a type II DNA topoisomerase from HeLa cell nuclei, using kinetoplast DNA networks as a substrate in a decatenation assay. The enzyme was a type II topoisomerase as demonstrated by its ability to change the linking number of DNA circles in steps of two and to decatenate or unknot covalently closed DNA circles. Further, they did not detect any gyrase activity. They also observed that ATP was required for the relaxation, decatenation, and unknotting of DNA, and a DNA-dependent ATPase activity was present in the most pure fractions.

Evidence supports a defect at the level of chromatin structure or recognition of that structure in cells from patients with the human genetic disorder ataxia-telangiectasia. In Epstein Barr Virus-transformed lymphoblastoid cells from patients with this syndrome, Singh et al. [16] investigated the activities of enzymes that alter the topology of DNA. They observed reduced activity of DNA topoisomerase II, determined by unknitting of P4 phage DNA, in partially purified extracts from 5 ataxia-telangiectasia cell lines. They also found DNA topoisomerase I to be present at comparable levels in both cell types, assayed by relaxation of supercoiled DNA. Further, reduced activity of topoisomerase II in ataxia-telangiectasia was compatible with the molecular, cellular and clinical changes described in this syndrome.

Tsai-Pflugfelder et al. [17] identified two overlapping cDNA clones encoding human DNA topoisomerase II, via two independent methods. Hybridization between the cloned sequences and mRNA and genomic DNA indicated that the human enzyme was encoded by a single-copy gene and the location of the gene was mapped to chromosome 17q21-22 by in situ hybridization of a cloned fragment to metaphase chromosomes and by hybridization analysis with a panel of mouse-human hybrid cell lines, each retaining a subset of human chromosomes.

Chung et al. [18] sequenced several DNA topoisomerase II (Topo II; EC 5.99.1.3) partial cDNA clones, obtained from a human Raji-HN2 cDNA library and found two classes of nucleotide sequences. Their data provided genetic and immunochemical evidence for two Topo II isozymes.

HL-60/AMSA is a human leukemia cell line that is 50- to 100-fold more resistant to the cytotoxic actions of the topoisomerase II-reactive intercalator amsacrine than is its drug-sensitive HL-60 parent line. Previously, Hinds et al. [19] had shown that the topoisomerase II from HL-60/AMSA was also resistant to inhibition by amsacrine and other intercalating agents. They therefore sought the molecular basis for the resistance of the topoisomerase II of HL-60/AMSA and, by inference, of the HL-60/AMSA line itself. Consequently, Hinds et al. [19] reported the cloning and sequencing of the topoisomerase II genes from both the sensitive and resistant leukemia cell lines using polymerase chain reaction technology, and identified a single base change associated with the drug-resistant form of topoisomerase II. They developed a rapid assay for this mutation in clinical samples and applied to the DNA of cells from both normal volunteers and leukemia patients, and it is thought that it will allow a rapid search for the prevalence of this mutation in clinical samples from patients with leukemia who have relapsed following intercalator therapy.

Human cells contain two topoisomerase II isozymes named topo II α and topo II β . Tan et al. [20] cloned the complementary DNAs for both enzymes. The human topo II α gene has previously been mapped to chromosome 17 and Tan et al. [20] confirmed the chromosomal location of topo II α and mapped the topo II β gene to chromosome 3.

Human topoisomerase II α (TOP2A) is encoded by the TOP2A gene on chromosome 17q21-22, and human topoisomerase II β (TOP2B) is encoded by the TOP2B gene on chromosome 3p24. Lang et al. [21] defined the intron-exon structures of TOP2A and TOP2B. Alignment of the amino-acid sequences of the two proteins indicated that the intron-exon organization of the two genes was highly conserved, except for the regions encoding the extreme NH₂ and COOH termini of the proteins.

These findings suggested strongly that the vertebrate isoforms evolved by duplication of an ancestral gene. They hypothesize that knowledge of the genomic organization of TOP2A and TOP2B would be useful for detection of mutations in clinical samples from patients with drug-resistant malignant disease.

In the nucleus of the cell, core RNA polymerase II (pol II) is associated with a large complex called the pol II holoenzyme (holo-pol). Transcription by core pol II in vitro on nucleosomal templates was repressed compared with that on templates of histone-free naked DNA. Mondal and Parvin [22] found that the transcriptional activity of holo-pol, in contrast to that of core pol II, was not markedly repressed on chromatin templates. They referred this property of holo-pol as chromatin-dependent coactivation (CDC) and showed that DNA topoisomerase II α was associated with the holo-pol and was a required component of CDC. Specific inhibitors of topoisomerase II, blocked transcription on chromatin templates, while addition of purified topoisomerase II α reconstituted CDC activity in reactions with core pol II. Their findings suggested that transcription on chromatin templates resulted in the accumulation of superhelical tension, making the relaxation activity of topoisomerase II essential for productive RNA synthesis on nucleosomal DNA.

DNA topoisomerase II completely removes DNA intertwinings, or catenations, between sister chromatids before they are segregated during cell division. Baxter et al. [23] demonstrated in yeast, that centromeric plasmids underwent a dramatic change in their topology as the cells passed through mitosis. This change was characterized by positive supercoiling of the DNA and required mitotic spindles and the condensin factor SMC2. When mitotic positive supercoiling occurred on decatenated DNA, it was rapidly relaxed by topoisomerase II. However, when positive supercoiling took place in catenated plasmid, topoisomerase II activity was directed toward decatenation of the molecules before relaxation. Thus, they observed that a topological change on DNA drove topoisomerase II to decatenate molecules during mitosis, potentially driving the full decatenation of the genome.

Nuclear factor (NF)-YB, a subunit of the transcription factor nuclear factor Y (NF-Y) complex, binds and activates CCAAT-containing promoters. In a previous work, Chen et al. [24] suggested that NF-YB may be a mediator of topoisomerase II α (TOP2A), working through the TOP2A promoter. TOP2 is the primary target for several clinically important anticancer drugs and their teniposide-resistant human lymphoblastic leukemia CEM cells (CEM/VM-1-5) expressed reduced TOP2A protein compared with parental CEM cells. To study the regulation of TOP2A, during the development of drug resistance, they found that NF-YB protein expression was increased in CEM/VM-1-5 cells compared with parental CEM cells. Their's was the first study to show that miR-485-3p mediated TOP2A down-regulation in part by altered regulation of NF-YB.

Dykhuisen et al. [25] showed that endogenous BAF complexes interact directly with endogenous TOP2A, through BAF250a and are required for the binding of TOP2A to approximately 12,000 sites across the genome. Their results demonstrated that TOP2A chromatin binding was dependent on the ATPase activity of BRG1, which was compromised in oncogenic BRG1 mutants. Thus, these studies indicated that the ability of TOP2A to prevent DNA entanglement at mitosis required BAF complexes and suggested that this activity contributed to the role of BAF subunits as tumour sup-

processors.

TOP2 DNA transactions proceed via formation of the TOP2 cleavage complex (TOP2cc), a covalent enzyme-DNA reaction intermediate that is vulnerable to trapping by potent anticancer TOP2 drugs. While trying to understand how genotoxic TOP2 DNA-protein cross-links are resolved, Schellenberg et al. [26] found that the small ubiquitin-related modifier (SUMO) ligase ZATT (ZNF451) was a multifunctional DNA repair factor that controlled cellular responses to TOP2 damage. They observed that ZATT binding to TOP2cc facilitated a proteasome-independent tyrosyl-DNA phosphodiesterase 2 (TDP2) hydrolase activity on stalled TOP2cc. The ZATT SUMO ligase activity further promoted TDP2 interactions with SUMOylated TOP2, regulating efficient TDP2 recruitment through a "split-SIM" SUMO2 engagement platform. These findings uncovered a ZATT-TDP2-catalyzed and SUMO2-modulated pathway for direct resolution of TOP2cc.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [27] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene

combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [28] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [28].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [29]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have

been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [30], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [27] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [27]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [31], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. TOP2A related synergies

Note - TOP2A was found to be upregulated in Type C. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 258 2^{nd} order combinations of TOP2A were recorded.

3.1.1. FOXM1/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3]

Meningioma is the most common primary intracranial tumor, but the molecular drivers of aggressive meningioma are incompletely understood. Using 280 human meningioma samples and RNA sequencing, immunohistochemistry, whole-exome sequencing, DNA methylation arrays, and targeted gene expression profiling, Vasudevan et al. [3] defined the molecular profile of aggressive meningioma. Their transcriptomic analyses identified FOXM1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes, while they discovered genomic and epigenomic factors associated with FOXM1 activation in aggressive meningiomas. Finally, they defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells.

Vasudevan et al. [3] provide a set of FOXM1 target genes in meningioma and they also defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells. Of these, CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2 (CKS2), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), cyclin B2 (CCNB2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), BUB1 mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase B (BUB1B), centromere protein F (CENPF), SPC25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25), kinesin family member 4A (KIF4A), NIMA related kinase 2 (NEK2), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), DEP domain containing 1B (DEPDC1B) and Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP), were found to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of TOP2A with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t TOP2A. CDCA5 - TOP2A shows high ranking of 247 (laplace), 237 (linear), 204 (rbf), 145 (jansen); KIF18B - TOP2A shows high ranking of 228 (laplace), 249 (linear), 146 (rbf), 118; and BRIP1 - TOP2A shows high ranking of 94, 155 (linear), 150 (rbf), 162(jansen).

While, CKS2 - TOP2A shows low ranking of 130, 162, 123, 190; TPX2 - TOP2A shows low ranking of 146, 50, 160, 213; CCNB2 - TOP2A shows low ranking of 157, 97, 122, 237; TROAP - TOP2A shows low ranking of 89, 171, 74, 180; TK1 - TOP2A shows low ranking of 73, 173, 131, 166; BUB1B - TOP2A shows low ranking of 28, 174, 128, 188; CENPF - TOP2A shows low ranking of 25, 70, 96, 155; SPC25 - TOP2A shows low ranking of 111, 55, 87, 18; KIF4A - TOP2A shows low ranking of 131, 68, 30, 248; NEK2 - TOP2A shows low ranking of 122, 89, 142, 242; and DEPDC1B - TOP2A shows low ranking of 44, 202, 32, 78.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t TOP2A with TOP2A – > CDCA5 / KIF18B / BRIP1.

3.1.2. TOP2A unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by TOP2A, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [1]. I document here, the 2nd order combinations with TOP2A, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the TOP2A and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, ST3 beta-galactoside alpha-2,3-sialyltransferase 6 (ST3GAL6), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), neuron navigator 1 (NAV1), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 39 (ARHGEF39), centrosomal protein 55 (CEP55), cartilage intermediate layer protein (CILP), denticleless E3 ubiquitin protein ligase homolog (DTL), LHFPL tetraspan subfamily member 2 (LHFPL2), ankyrin repeat domain 31 (ANKRD31), cell division cycle associ-

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TOP2A

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TOP2A				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CKS2 - TOP2A	130	162	123	190
TPX2 - TOP2A	146	50	160	213
CCNB2 - TOP2A	157	97	122	237
CDCA5 - TOP2A	247	237	204	145
TROAP - TOP2A	89	171	74	180
TK1 - TOP2A	73	173	131	166
BUB1B - TOP2A	28	174	128	188
CENPF - TOP2A	25	70	96	155
SPC25 - TOP2A	111	55	87	18
KIF4A - TOP2A	131	68	30	248
NEK2 - TOP2A	122	89	142	242
KIF18B - TOP2A	228	249	146	118
BRIP1 - TOP2A	94	155	150	162
DEPDC1B - TOP2A	44	202	32	78

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between TOP2A VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t TOP2A	
CDCA5	TOP2A
KIF18B	TOP2A
BRIP1	TOP2A

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TOP2A and Individual members.

ated 5 (CDCA5), pantothenate kinase 1 (PANK1), pleckstrin homology and RhoGEF domain containing G4B (PLEKHG4B), diacylglycerol kinase iota (DGKI), thymosin beta 15A (TMSB15A), solute carrier family 13 member 3 (SLC13A3), plexin domain containing 1 (PLXDC1), tubulin epsilon and delta complex 2 (TEDC2), ribo-

somal protein L22 like 1 (RPL22L1), PTTG1 regulator of sister chromatid separation, securin (PTTG1), solute carrier family 29 member 4 (SLC29A4), spindle and kinetochore associated complex subunit 3 (SKA3), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 1 (HACD1), chromatin licensing and DNA replication factor 1 (CDT1), PDZ binding kinase (PBK), cytoskeleton associated protein 2 like (CKAP2L), ribonucleotide reductase regulatory subunit M2 (RRM2), aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear translocator 2 (ARNT2), ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2 C (UBE2C), ETS variant transcription factor 4 (ETV4), H2A clustered histone 6 (HIST1H2AC), neurexophilin 4 (NXPH4), collagen type XVIII alpha 1 chain (COL18A1), immunoglobulin superfamily member 5 (IGSF5), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), ERCC excision repair 6 like, spindle assembly checkpoint helicase (ERCC6L), FAM111 trypsin like peptidase B (FAM111B), spire type actin nucleation factor 2 (SPIRE2), SRRM2 antisense RNA 1 (SRRM2-AS1), microRNA 635 (MIR635), Ewing sarcoma associated transcript 1 (EWSAT1), tripartite motif containing 59 (TRIM59), reticulocalbin 1 pseudogene 2 (RCN1P2), MCM3AP antisense RNA 1 (MCM3AP-AS1), PITX1 antisense RNA 1 (C5orf66), KMT2E antisense RNA 1 (LINC01004), DARS1 antisense RNA 1 (DARS-AS1), NALCN antisense RNA 1 (NALCN-AS1), NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit B1 pseudogene 2 (NDUFB1P2), small regulatory polypeptide of amino acid response (SPAAR), small Cajal body-specific RNA 7 (SCARNA7), thioredoxin domain containing 5 (TXNDC5), CDKN2B and CDKN2A antisense cis and trans regulatory RNA 1 (CDKN2B-AS1), RRS1 divergent transcript (RRS1-AS1), and long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1948 (LINC01948), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of TOP2A with these genes.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t TOP2A.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t TOP2A with TOP2A – > ST3GAL6 / TPX2 / NAV1 / BRIP1 / ARHGEF39 / CEP55 / CILP / DTL / LHFPL2 / ANKRD31 / CDCA5 / PANK1 / PLEKHG4B / DGKI / TMSB15A / SLC13A3 / PLXDC1 / TEDC2 / RPL22L1 / PTTG1 / SLC29A4 / SKA3 / HACD1 / CDT1 / PBK / CKAP2L / RRM2 / ARNT2 / UBE2C / ETV4 / HIST1H2AC / NXPH4 / COL18A1 / IGSF5 / KIF18B / ERCC6L / FAM111B / SPIRE2 / SRRM2-AS1 / MIR635 / EWSAT1 / TRIM59 / RCN1P2 / MCM3AP-AS1 / C5orf66 / LINC01004 / DARS-AS1 / NALCN-AS1 / NDUFB1P2 / SPAAR / SCARNA7 / TXNDC5 / CDKN2B-AS1 / RRS1-AS1 / LINC01948.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic TOP2A 2^{nd} order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of TOP2A-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TOP2A									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TOP2A									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ST3GAL6 - TOP2A	148	45	196	231	TPX2 - TOP2A	146	50	160	213
NAV1 - TOP2A	221	192	59	249	BRIP1 - TOP2A	94	155	150	162
ARHGEF39 - TOP2A	202	166	71	211	CEP55 - TOP2A	97	252	217	144
CILP - TOP2A	104	220	162	232	DTL - TOP2A	160	164	168	109
LHFPL2 - TOP2A	169	128	240	251	ANKRD31 - TOP2A	134	186	158	21
CDCA5 - TOP2A	247	237	204	145	PANK1 - TOP2A	106	232	189	152
PLEKHG4B - TOP2A	235	178	173	85	DGKI - TOP2A	194	212	191	113
TMSB15A - TOP2A	65	219	180	207	SLC13A3 - TOP2A	165	167	92	256
PLXDC1 - TOP2A	193	255	110	159	TEDC2 - TOP2A	142	253	119	258
RPL22L1 - TOP2A	177	170	78	225	PTTG1 - TOP2A	172	91	167	214
SLC29A4 - TOP2A	74	165	197	247	SKA3 - TOP2A	163	193	178	184
HACD1 - TOP2A	173	110	192	216	CDT1 - TOP2A	161	199	54	193
PBK - TOP2A	186	39	152	209	CKAP2L - TOP2A	182	230	231	229
RRM2 - TOP2A	156	245	220	238	ARNT2 - TOP2A	212	139	193	19
UBE2C - TOP2A	190	126	218	230	ETV4 - TOP2A	214	172	206	17
HIST1H2AC - TOP2A	246	150	222	71	NXPH4 - TOP2A	211	147	224	23
COL18A1 - TOP2A	210	210	242	33	IGSF5 - TOP2A	197	161	181	72
KIF18B - TOP2A	228	249	146	118	ERCC6L - TOP2A	96	239	226	257
FAM111B - TOP2A	43	207	149	204	SPIRE2 - TOP2A	39	224	137	182
SRRM2-AS1 - TOP2A	166	134	234	138	MIR635 - TOP2A	56	240	201	157
EWSAT1 - TOP2A	187	69	252	241	TRIM59 - TOP2A	61	213	185	235
RCN1P2 - TOP2A	14	258	166	156	MCM3AP-AS1 - TOP2A	147	184	76	221
C5orf66 - TOP2A	171	251	156	202	LINC01004 - TOP2A	75	190	212	172
DARS-AS1 - TOP2A	257	115	157	219	NALCN-AS1 - TOP2A	213	205	257	170
NDUFB1P2 - TOP2A	87	246	195	175	SPAAR - TOP2A	105	242	186	212
SCARNA7 - TOP2A	150	146	126	197	TXNDC5 - TOP2A	127	163	175	252
CDKN2B-AS1 - TOP2A	67	177	176	199	RRS1-AS1 - TOP2A	153	169	182	11
LINC01948 - TOP2A	91	181	209	200					

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between TOP2A VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Unknown Individual members w.r.t TOP2A	
ST3GAL6 / TPX2 / NAV1 / BRIP1 / ARHGEF39 ...	
CEP55 / CILP / DTL / LHFPL2 / ANKRD31 ...	
CDCA5 / PANK1 / PLEKHG4B / DGKI / TMSB15A ...	
SLC13A3 / PLXDC1 / TEDC2 / RPL22L1 / PTTG1 ...	
SLC29A4 / SKA3 / HACD1 / CDT1 / PBK / CKAP2L ...	
RRM2 / ARNT2 / UBE2C / ETV4 / HIST1H2AC / NXPH4 ...	
COL18A1 / IGSF5 / KIF18B / ERCC6L / FAM111B ...	
SPIRE2 / SRRM2-AS1 / MIR635 / EWSAT1 / TRIM59 ...	
RCN1P2 / MCM3AP-AS1 / C5orf66 / LINC01004 ...	
DARS-AS1 / NALCN-AS1 / NDUFB1P2 / SPAAR / SCARNA7 ...	
TXNDC5 / CDKN2B-AS1 / RRS1-AS1 / LINC01948	
TOP2A	

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TOP2A and Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

5. References

References

- [1] A. J. Patel, Y.-W. Wan, R. Al-Ouran, J.-P. Revelli, M. F. Cardenas, M. Oneissi, L. Xi, A. Jalali, J. F. Magnotti, D. M. Muzny, et al., Molecular profiling predicts meningioma recurrence and reveals loss of dream complex repression in aggressive tumors, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 116 (2019) 21715–21726.
- [2] S. Sinha, Machine learning ranking of plausible (un) explored synergistic gene combinations using sensitivity indices of time series measurements of wnt signaling pathway, *Integrative Biology* 16 (2024) zya020.
- [3] H. N. Vasudevan, S. E. Braunstein, J. J. Phillips, M. Pekmezci, B. A. Tomlin, A. Wu, G. F. Reis, S. T. Magill, J. Zhang, F. Y. Feng, et al., Comprehensive molecular profiling identifies foxm1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation, *Cell reports* 22 (2018) 3672–3683.
- [4] D. N. Louis, A. Perry, P. Wesseling, D. J. Brat, I. A. Cree, D. Figarella-Branger, C. Hawkins, H. Ng, S. M. Pfister, G. Reifenberger, et al., The 2021 who classification of tumors of the central nervous system: a summary, *Neuro-oncology* 23 (2021) 1231–1251.
- [5] S. H. Torp, O. Solheim, A. J. Skjulsvik, The who 2021 classification of central nervous system tumours: a practical update on what neurosurgeons need to know a minireview, *Acta Neurochirurgica* 164 (2022) 2453–2464.
- [6] A. Czarnetzki, E. Schwaderer, C. M. Pusch, Fossil record of meningioma, *The Lancet* 362 (2003) 408.

- [7] D. O. Okonkwo, E. R. Laws Jr, Meningiomas: historical perspective, in: Meningiomas, Springer, 2009, pp. 3–10.
- [8] S. Paterniti, Meningiomas surgery in Italy in the nineteenth century: Historical review, *Austin Neurosurg Open Access* 2 (2015) 1030.
- [9] Z. Pecchioli, Soria di un fungo della dura madre, operato collettirpazione dal professor zanobi pecchioli, *Nuovo Giornale de'LetteratiScienze* 36 (1838) 39–44.
- [10] H. Cushing, The meningiomas (dural endotheliomas): their source, and favoured seats of origin, *Brain* 45 (1922) 282–316.
- [11] W. contributors, Meningioma — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, 2024. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Meningioma&oldid=1259055917>, online; accessed 11-April-2025.
- [12] M. N. Pamir, P. M. Black, R. Fahlbusch, Meningiomas : a comprehensive text, Elsevier Health Sciences, 2010.
- [13] F. Szulzewsky, H. N. Thirimanne, E. C. Holland, Meningioma: current updates on genetics, classification, and mouse modeling, *Upsala Journal of Medical Sciences* 129 (2024) 10–48101.
- [14] L. F. Liu, C.-C. Liu, B. M. Alberts, T4 dna topoisomerase: a new atp-dependent enzyme essential for initiation of t4 bacteriophage dna replication, *Nature* 281 (1979) 456–461.
- [15] K. G. Miller, L. F. Liu, P. T. Englund, A homogeneous type ii dna topoisomerase from hela cell nuclei., *Journal of biological chemistry* 256 (1981) 9334–9339.
- [16] S. P. Singh, R. Mohamed, C. Salmond, M. Lavin, Reduced dna topoisomerase ii activity in ataxia-telangiectasia cells, *Nucleic acids research* 16 (1988) 3919–3929.
- [17] M. Tsai-Pflugfelder, L. F. Liu, A. A. Liu, K. M. Tewey, J. Whang-Peng, T. Knutsen, K. Huebner, C. M. Croce, J. C. Wang, Cloning and sequencing of cDNA encoding human dna topoisomerase ii and localization of the gene to chromosome region 17q21-22., *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 85 (1988) 7177–7181.
- [18] T. Chung, F. H. Drake, K. Tan, S. R. Per, S. T. Crooke, C. K. Mirabelli, Characterization and immunological identification of cDNA clones encoding two human dna topoisomerase ii isozymes., *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 86 (1989) 9431–9435.
- [19] M. Hinds, K. Deisseroth, J. Mayes, E. Altschuler, R. Jansen, F. D. Ledley, L. A. Zwellung, Identification of a point mutation in the topoisomerase ii gene from a human leukemia cell line containing an amsacrine-resistant form of topoisomerase ii, *Cancer research* 51 (1991) 4729–4731.

- [20] K. Tan, T. E. Dorman, K. M. Falls, T. D. Chung, C. K. Mirabelli, S. T. Crooke, J.-i. Mao, Topoisomerase $ii\alpha$ and topoisomerase $ii\beta$ genes: characterization and mapping to human chromosomes 17 and 3, respectively, *Cancer Research* 52 (1992) 231–234.
- [21] A. Lang, S. Mirski, H. Cummings, Q. Yu, J. Gerlach, S. Cole, Structural organization of the human top2a and top2b genes, *Gene* 221 (1998) 255–266.
- [22] N. Mondal, J. D. Parvin, Dna topoisomerase $ii\alpha$ is required for rna polymerase ii transcription on chromatin templates, *Nature* 413 (2001) 435–438.
- [23] J. Baxter, N. Sen, V. L. Martínez, M. M. De Carandini, J. B. Schwartzman, J. F. Diffley, L. Aragón, Positive supercoiling of mitotic dna drives decatenation by topoisomerase ii in eukaryotes, *Science* 331 (2011) 1328–1332.
- [24] C.-F. Chen, X. He, A. D. Arslan, Y.-Y. Mo, W. C. Reinhold, Y. Pommier, W. T. Beck, Novel regulation of nuclear factor- γ by mir-485-3p affects the expression of dna topoisomerase $ii\alpha$ and drug responsiveness, *Molecular pharmacology* 79 (2011) 735–741.
- [25] E. C. Dykhuizen, D. C. Hargreaves, E. L. Miller, K. Cui, A. Korshunov, M. Kool, S. Pfister, Y.-J. Cho, K. Zhao, G. R. Crabtree, Baf complexes facilitate decatenation of dna by topoisomerase $ii\alpha$, *Nature* 497 (2013) 624–627.
- [26] M. J. Schellenberg, J. A. Lieberman, A. Herrero-Ruiz, L. R. Butler, J. G. Williams, A. M. Muñoz-Cabello, G. A. Mueller, R. E. London, F. Cortés-Ledesma, R. S. Williams, Zatt (znf451)-mediated resolution of topoisomerase 2 dna-protein cross-links, *Science* 357 (2017) 1412–1416.
- [27] T. Joachims, Training linear svms in linear time, in: Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining, ACM, 2006, pp. 217–226.
- [28] G. Pujol, B. Iooss, A. Janon, K. Boumhaout, S. Da Veiga, J. Fruth, L. Gilquin, J. Guillaume, L. Le Gratiet, P. Lemaitre, et al., Sensitivity: global sensitivity analysis of model outputs, R package version 1 (2017).
- [29] H. Huang, Y. Liu, M. Yuan, J. Marron, Statistical significance of clustering using soft thresholding, *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics* 24 (2015) 975–993.
- [30] S. Sinha, Hilbert-schmidt and sobol sensitivity indices for static and time series wnt signaling measurements in colorectal cancer-part a, *BMC systems biology* 11 (2017) 120.
- [31] R. C. Team, R language definition, Vienna, Austria: R foundation for statistical computing 3 (2000) 116.